

Conservation work on Hamburg's last tram

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Previous history

Hamburg had one of the oldest and most extensive German tram networks. The first electrically-powered line was opened as early as 1894. In 1958, the Senate of the Hansestadt Hamburg decided to close down the entire network; the last route was converted to a bus service in 1978. Several depots were converted to building supplies stores and supermarkets. When the last tram depot in Old Kollaustrasse in Lokstedt became a DIY store, a “conservation light” approach was applied.

Illustration 1 A last look at the Lokstedt depot on the afternoon of 01 October 1978

Illustration 2 After completion of restoration work and opening of the DIY store

The restoration concept

The tram was handed over to Bauhaus GmbH und Co KG by the Hamburger Hochbahn AG on a long-term loan for 30 years, on condition that the borrower pay for the restoration. The tram is now located in its former environment, a tram depot surrounded by a DIY store, a branch of Bauhaus. A small exhibition on the history of the Hamburg tram network will be set up in the near future. In order to present the tram as a representative of its type, the aim was to restore and complete¹ the whole vehicle, above and beyond the conservation of the materials. The priority was not to negate the tram's patina and age, but to make them visible. Faulty areas which impede the perception of the tram's overall form and design were repaired. The aim was to give the impression of an article of use which has been carefully looked after.

Description of the tram's state

Roof

When restoration work started, the roof had already been removed in separate pieces. The insulators and covering panels had been unscrewed and stored in the car. The current collector was fixed to a roof bow. Many of the materials were in a decayed state. The catwalk of wooden strips was rotten and in some places there were signs of damage from brown cubical rot.

Illustration 3 Condition of the tram before restoration

Leaves had collected under the wood and partly composted. Moss and lichen were growing on parts of the metal roof surface. The steel panels were also heavily corroded, particularly at the sides. The original paint was flaking or undermined by corrosion. Under the insulators, the roof is covered with a thick plastic sheet which was also dirty. Loudspeakers mounted on the roof hung open. The protective netting of one loudspeaker was torn. The housing of the destination display was dented from above, which had destroyed the glass cover. Some glass splinters had cut the destination blind underneath.

¹ 'Complete' in the sense that existing parts that had been removed were remounted

Outer skin around the vehicle

The tram's red and beige outer skin was damaged in over 50 places. In places where adhesive signs² had been attached under the paint, only the top red coat had peeled. In other places, the red coat and the filler coat underneath had been damaged by external impacts. Many spots were undermined by rust. At the front, the bar between the windscreen and the destination display was broken. Corrosion had left holes in the metal skin in some places under the beige paint.

Illustration 4: Deep hole with signs of external impact

Illustration 5: Broken frame above the driver's windscreen. The metal sheet is corroded through in places.

One side of the tram was covered with a line of white graffiti over almost the entire length. A lot of sandy, dusty dirt had collected on the outer skin in the lower parts below the doors or above the wheels. Some of the windows were broken. Most of the cracks were small and old, as could be seen from the dark broken edges. One window had been damaged only a short time previously and the cracks covered almost the whole pane.

Underbody

The tram's underbody was very dirty with earth, dust and oily residues.

Interior

The interior was fully preserved. All the seats and the equipment in the driver's cab were still present. Some ceiling coverings, handrails, side boxes and lamp glass had been removed. The interior was very dirty. The ceiling panels and windows were covered with a grey film of dirt. The floor was dirty and covered with mouse droppings. The wooden side walls and the rear sides of the wooden seat backs were infested with white mould. The handrails of the wooden seats were very corroded. The adhesive film covering some of the advertising posters on the tram windows was yellowed. Both tram network maps in the driver's cab and on the car roof were dirty, torn and peeling off the surface. The sign saying "Passengers without a valid ticket are requested to pay the driver" had been removed and lay on the seats. The rear step was loose.

² Advertising sign by Idee Kaffee coffee company

Illustration 6: View of the interior looking towards the driver's cab before restoration

Illustration 7: Rear part of the car; white mould can be seen on the walls

Taking over the tram

When we first looked at it, the tram was under a roof on the premises of Usinger + Trombetta GmbH, a removals company. After preliminary cleaning by TrikonBerlin using a high-pressure cleaner, the removals company brought the tram to the building site. It was shrink-wrapped to protect it against vandalism until restoration work could begin.

Illustration 8: The tram in the depot on the Usinger + Trombetta premises, ready to be loaded onto the flat-bed truck

Illustration 9: The tram in its final location, still shrink-wrapped

Measures applied

Roof

First, the whole roof was given a preliminary clean with a high-pressure cleaner. The damaged areas where the roof coating was undermined by rust were cleaned, the rust removed and coated with an anti-corrosion primer³. Where the distance between the paint and metal was too great it was bridged with polyester filler. Then the metal roof was painted with a single coat of mica-iron paint in the shade DB 701. To protect the coating against humidity, anti-corrosive wax⁴ was applied using a cup gun sprayer. Finally the surface was brushed to compact it.

³ Phosphate paint Maxolan 720 by Maleco Farbwerke Hamburg

⁴ Conrads Lacke, anti-corrosion wax

The insulators were cleaned and remounted in their original positions. The rust was removed from the covering panels and they were coated in the same way as the rest of the roof (see above). The panels were remounted in their original positions above the insulators.

Illustration 10: The roof before restoration

Illustration 11: The roof after restoration

Some replacement wooden strips were made, retouched and mounted. The torn loudspeaker cover was lined with fabric which was then glued on and retouched. The loudspeaker was remounted. The broken glass and rubber seal on the side destination display were removed. The housing was bent back into its original shape. The cuts in the destination blind were lined with fabric which was then retouched. Finally, new glass was inserted.

Exterior skin

The entire exterior skin was first cleaned of dirt and encrustations using a high-pressure cleaner. Rust spots in the outer skin were first cleaned off and coated with an anti-corrosive primer. Then they were filled to the correct depth with reversible filler⁵. Next, they were retouched with synthetic resin single-coat varnish. The retouching colours used were red: RAL 3000 fire red and beige: RAL 1001 beige. The paint was mixed with brown, blue or white pigments to match the surrounding colour nuances. Finally, anti-corrosive wax was applied and the surface compacted with microfiber cloth. The graffiti on one side of the tram was removed using ethyl acetate and cotton buds. The broken window was replaced.

Illustration 12: Damaged area on the outer skin before restoration

Illustration 13: During restoration. Filler is applied, smoothed and superfluous material removed

Illustration 14: After filling, retouching, and sealing the surface with wax

⁵ Filler made of chalk from Champagne and synthetic resin Paraloid B72 dissolved in ethyl acetate

Underbody

The underbody was given a preliminary clean with a high-pressure cleaner, then cleaned more thoroughly with a vacuum cleaner and spatula. Finally it was coated with anti-corrosion wax applied using a cup gun spray.

Interior

In the interior, a new wiring harness was installed to all the round lamps and energy-saving lightbulbs (9V) inserted. The original lightbulb in the driver's cab was yellow, so it was replaced with a yellow bulb. The wiring harness was routed to the underbody, where the electrician could link the lighting to the tram's internal power supply. All ceiling panels, decorative strips and lamps were remounted.

The seats and wooden cladding were wiped with a solution of 80% water and 20% Isopropanol to combat mould. The rest of the interior cladding and the rubber floor covering were wiped with a moist sponge with water and detergent.

The corroded handrails were cleaned with fine steel wool; peeling chrome layers were secured with synthetic resin, Paraloid B72 in ethyl acetate, and all iron pieces inside the tram were coated with anti-corrosion wax and compacted.

The cover of the driver's seat was cleaned using a vacuum cleaner and a small brush. Wooden parts where the adhesive had come off were re-glued on using PVAC white glue. The felt of the ticket bag was cleaned using a vacuum cleaner and paintbrush. Japanese tissue paper was used to line the torn leather strap and glued on with acrylic adhesive⁶.

An advertising poster attached to the broken window was carefully removed and attached to the replacement pane with self-adhesive film. Another advertising poster was removed from its yellowed adhesive film, cleaned with Isopropanol and cotton buds and remounted in the same place.

The network map was lined with Japanese tissue paper and glued on with acrylic glue (see above) to stabilise the tears. Then the remains of the former adhesive film could be removed using a swab soaked in ethyl acetate and a scalpel.

Summary

The net cost of the restoration work was 25,100 euros. Including German VAT at 19%, the total is approx. 30,000 euros. Three restorers each worked nine hours a day for three weeks on the tram.

Thank you for your attention.

Biography Gesa Witt

Apprenticeship as a professional Metal worker in Berlin. Studys of Conservation of Technical Heritage at the University of Applied Sciences, Berlin. Diploma in Conservation of Technical Heritage, Subject: The Conservation of a Mechanical Advertising Automaton.

Temporary employments abroad as a Scholarship from the Carl – Duisberg – Association in Togo, Africa. Collaboration with the welders and coachbuilders of a handicraft Organisation (3 month) and a Scholarship from Inwent in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil at the Conservation Studio of the “Museu de Astronomia e Ciências Afins”. Supervision and conservation of the collection of astronomical equipment. (6 month)

Since 2009 setting up the Network of technical conservators “TriKonBerlin” together with Ulrich Stahn. Working self- employed with an own workshop in many different restauration projects.